

Research Article

GeniusBin – A Smart Waste Management

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Abstract: Malaysia, as a developing country, continues to face challenges in managing waste properly, especially in urban areas. As there are many industrial hubs located in these urban areas, the people who live there come from various educational backgrounds and a significant number of foreign workers, many of whom show little concern for proper waste disposal practices. The issue is further worsened by weak law enforcement, which allows irresponsible waste management to continue unchecked. Moreover, the cost borne by the municipality for rubbish collection and disposal is considerably expensive, which sometimes leads to irregular schedules and overflow of the bins. This scenario not only spoils the cleanliness and image of cities but also leads to serious environmental problems such as pollution, clogged drainage systems, increased risk of diseases, and reduced property values. Therefore, this project introduces an innovative solution called “GeniusBin – A smart waste management” to mitigate these issues. A prototype in the form of a bin that comprises of ESP32 microcontroller, ultrasonic sensors, and LED light was designed to prevent waste overflow and enhance the efficiency of waste management. The front sensor of the bin, which is located near the lid detects hand or object movement, allowing it to open and close automatically for hygienic operation. An internal sensor monitors the bin fill level; once full, it notifies municipal authorities and activates a red indicator of light to signal maintenance needs. This solution may minimize environmental pollution, public health risks, and visual degradation in urban areas by ensuring timely waste collection and reducing overflow occurrences. For future improvement, we plan to integrate a solar panel to make it a self-sustaining model and contributes to Malaysia’s effort in smart city development.

Keywords: waste management; smart city; Internet of Things (IoT).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Managing waste properly is still one of the major problems in Malaysia (Ghazali et al., 2025). The common sight of overflowing public bins and irregular waste collection schedules pollutes our environment, makes our neighbourhoods unpleasant, and creates serious health risks. This pile-up of trash is a perfect breeding ground for pests. These pests, like rats and flies, can increase the transmission

of pathogens and spread diseases like cholera, dysentery, malaria and dengue (Abubakar et al., 2022). Beyond the immediate health concerns, the environmental impact is equally severe. When waste is not contained properly, it pollutes local ecosystems. Plastic and other harmful materials often end up in natural habitats, where wildlife often eats or gets tangled in this waste, leading to widespread injury and death (Garcês & Pires, 2024).

A central weakness in the current system is the reliance on conventional, non-monitored bins. These bins lack any monitoring capabilities; they provide no feedback on their fill status. This lack of information is the direct cause of waste overflow, creating unhygienic conditions and inconvenience for the public. To address these inefficiencies, modern solutions are increasingly focused on the Internet of Things (IoT) to create intelligent, smart waste management systems (Guo, 2024). Our project, the 'GeniusBin,' introduces an innovative prototype built on this exact principle. The 'GeniusBin' is an IoT-based automated smart bin designed to tackle waste overflow and enhance management efficiency. The system is equipped with two primary functions reviewed in existing literature (Abhishek et al., 2025). First, for hygienic, touchless operation, a sensor detects an approaching hand or object and triggers a servo motor to open the lid automatically. Second, an internal ultrasonic sensor constantly monitors the bin's fill level. Once the bin reaches its maximum capacity, it sends an immediate notification to municipal authorities via a Telegram bot and activates a red LED light to signal that it requires maintenance.

By providing real-time data and automating the user experience, the 'GeniusBin' aims to prevent waste overflow, ensure timely collection, and reduce the associated health and environmental hazards. This project demonstrates a practical and scalable solution that aligns with Malaysia's wider goals for sustainable and smart city development.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Methods

The GeniusBin prototype was developed following a series of design, assembly, and programming steps. The methodology can be divided into three main stages: hardware setup, software configuration, and system integration.

2.1.1 Hardware Setup

All electronic components were mounted on and around a small desktop dustbin. The front ultrasonic sensor was positioned near the upper lid to detect hand or object movement within a range of approximately 10–15 cm. The second ultrasonic sensor was installed at a certain level inside the bin, facing sideways. It is used to detect if the waste has reached the full level or not. The servo motor was attached to the lid via a stick and paper clip linkage, enabling it to lift and close the lid smoothly when activated. The red LED was fixed into the breadboard positioned at the side panel of the bin to signal when the bin reaches full capacity. All components were connected to the ESP32 board using jumper wires, a breadboard, and the system was powered and programmed through the USB cable. The completed setup is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

2.1.2 Software Configuration

The ESP32 microcontroller was programmed using the Arduino IDE platform. The front ultrasonic sensor detects motion within a defined range (approximately 10–15 cm). When a hand or object is detected, the ESP32 triggers the servo motor to open the lid automatically. After a short delay, typically 2–3 seconds, the lid closes to complete the disposal process. When the waste inside the bin

reaches the level of the internal sensor (full level), the bin will be considered as full. The ESP32 activates the red LED and sends an automated alert to the Telegram bot via Wi-Fi connectivity. The Telegram bot then notifies the municipal authority or maintenance staff in real time to ensure prompt waste collection.

2.1.3 System Integration and Testing

Once both hardware and software configurations were completed, the full system was assembled and tested. Initial tests verified the accuracy of the ultrasonic sensors in detecting motion and fill level. The servo motor's movement range and response time were calibrated to ensure smooth, reliable lid operation. The Telegram notification system was tested by simulating it by connecting it to the Wi-Fi, then the bot would send "ESP32 is online" message indicating it is ready to use. "The bin is FULL! Please empty it" message is sent when the internal sensor detects the waste has reached the full level and "The bin has been emptied" message would be sent by the telegram bot to confirm that the bin is now empty. These conditions confirmed that message is delivered successfully. The final prototype was observed under real-use scenarios to evaluate its reliability, hygiene improvement, and ability to prevent overflow. The sample screen is shown in Figure 3.

To summarize the whole operation, when a user approaches the bin, the front sensor detects motion, prompting the servo motor to open the lid automatically. After waste is deposited, the lid closes. The internal sensor monitors the bin's fill level; when full, the ESP32 triggers a red LED light and sends an alert message to municipal authorities via the Telegram bot, ensuring timely waste collection.

2.2 Hardware Materials

1. **ESP32:** Board acts as the main microcontroller and IoT module; processes sensor data and sends notifications to the municipal Telegram bot.
2. **Breadboard:** Serves as a base for building and testing the circuit without soldering; allows easy connection and rearrangement of components such as sensors, LED, and servo motor.
3. **Jumper wires:** Used for electrical connections between sensors, motor, LED, and the ESP32 board through the breadboard.
4. **USB cable:** Provides power and allows programming of the ESP32 board through a computer interface.
5. **Two ultrasonic sensors:** One sensor detects approaching objects or hands near the lid for automatic opening; the other monitors the waste fill level inside the bin.
6. **Servo motor:** Mechanically opens and closes the bin lid in response to signals from the front ultrasonic sensor.
7. **Red LED:** Serves as a visual indicator to alert maintenance staff when the bin is full.
8. **Stick:** Connects the servo motor arm to the dustbin lid, enabling motion transfer for lid movement.
9. **Paper clip:** Used as a mechanical connector or hinge reinforcement for the servo mechanism.
10. **Desktop dustbin:** Serves as the main container for the prototype, housing all sensors and hardware components.

3. FINDINGS

The completed prototype of the bin is as shown in Figure 1, where an ultrasonic sensor is placed at the front of the bin, providing touchless operation. When an object or hand is placed in front of the sensor, the lid will automatically open, reducing direct contact of hands with the bin surface for user convenience and hygiene.

Figure 1. GeniusBin prototype

Figure 2. Sensor inside GeniusBin

Figure 2 shows the internal view of the bin, where another ultrasonic sensor is placed inside the bin acting as a fill-level sensor to monitor waste level in the bin. When the bin is full, the red LED light is turned on as a visual indicator for user that the bin is full. A notification is sent to Telegram to automatically alert the local authorities that the bin is full, as shown in Figure 3. Once the bin is emptied, the red LED is turned off and another notification is sent to Telegram to inform that the bin has been emptied. With this feature, local authorities could easily monitor the performance of the appointed contractor for the waste collection job.

Figure 3. Telegram alert of GeniusBin

4. DISCUSSION

Bins that are overflowing not only harm the aesthetics of the environment but also present major health hazards to the public by acting as havens for disease vectors such as flies, mosquitoes, and rats. Diseases such as cholera, dysentery, malaria, and dengue are among the common diseases that can be spread by these vectors (Abubakar et al., 2022). Furthermore, waste that are not properly placed in bins might be consumed by stray animals or other wildlife and they might get tangled with the discarded plastics and other hazardous materials (Garcês & Pires, 2024).

By incorporating Internet of Things (IoT) technology for real-time waste monitoring and reporting, the GeniusBin overcomes these drawbacks. IoT-based waste systems improve operational

efficiency by streamlining collection routes and cutting down on needless labor, as mentioned in earlier studies (Guo, 2024; Abhishek et al., 2025). The GeniusBin's dual-purpose design, which combines fill-level detection and automated lid control, exemplifies how technological advancement can result in real environmental and public health advantages.

Additionally, placing these bins in urban locations such as parks, bus stops, and hallways would give residents convenient access to sanitary and clean waste disposal.

5. CONCLUSION

To sum up, the GeniusBin is a forward-thinking and useful waste management innovation. Waste overflow, unsanitary conditions, and ineffective collection procedures are common issues in Malaysia that might be successfully addressed by the system's integration of IoT technology, automation, and real-time communication.

In addition to helping local governments keep cities cleaner, this solution also improves public health, lowers pollution levels, and makes public areas more aesthetically pleasing. By incorporating solar panels in the future version of the prototype, could improve sustainability even more by allowing for independent and renewable energy source. This is in line with national sustainability agendas and Malaysia's Smart City Framework.

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